

STUDENTS' MOTIVATION TO LEARN AT THEIR CHOSEN FACULTY: A THEORETICAL AND CONTEXTUAL APPROACH

MOTIVAȚIA STUDENȚILOR DE A ÎNVĂȚA LA FACULTATEA ALEASĂ: O ABORDARE TEORETICĂ ȘI CONTEXTUALĂ

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Summary. *This article aims to explore the main theories of motivation – Self-Determination Theory, Expectancy-Value Theory, and Self-Efficacy Theory – in order to analyze students' learning behavior in relation to the faculty they have chosen. The analysis of these theoretical frameworks allows for the identification of the factors that influence the initiation, direction, intensity, and persistence of academic effort. It highlights the differences between intrinsic motivation, driven by personal interests, internal values, and passion for the field, and extrinsic motivation, influenced by external rewards, social pressures, or professional opportunities. The examples provided are anchored in the reality of students enrolled in tourism-related programs, illustrating how they structure their academic decisions based on perceived self-efficacy, the value assigned to the chosen field, and the degree of autonomy experienced in the educational process. Understanding these aspects contributes to the development of educational and institutional interventions that support students' authentic motivation and well-being within the university environment.*

Keywords: *motivation theories, students, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation.*

INTRODUCTION

Motivation, in general, is understood as a set of subjective experiences, either intrinsic or extrinsic in origin, through which we can explain the initiation, direction, intensity, and persistence of behavior aimed at achieving a goal. Applying this definition in the context of higher education, we can state that the choice of a university and the

commitment to the learning process are influenced by a variety of motivational factors that interact dynamically and differently depending on students' personal, social, and academic characteristics. Intrinsic motivation, expressed through curiosity, the desire for personal development, or a passion for a specific field of study, plays an essential role in maintaining long-term interest and building an authentic relationship with academic content. For example, a student who chooses a faculty based on the belief that the field reflects their personal values or professional aspirations is more likely to display deep commitment to the educational process.

On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is driven by external factors such as career prospects, social status, family influence, or anticipated material rewards. In many cases, the choice of university is guided by expectations related to professional insertion and job security, which leads students to adopt a performance- and outcome-oriented learning behavior, though sometimes lacking in personal satisfaction. In reality, students' motivation is rarely purely intrinsic or extrinsic, but rather the result of a complex combination of both dimensions. Factors such as institutional support, the quality of teaching, curricular relevance, opportunities for practical involvement, or the socio-emotional climate within the university can significantly influence the level and type of motivation demonstrated by students.

Building on these premises, the present article aims to analyze the main theories of motivation in order to gain a deeper understanding of how student learning behavior can be explained in relation to the faculty they have chosen. Exploring these theoretical frameworks allows us to identify the factors that determine the initiation, direction, intensity, and persistence of academic effort, as well as to distinguish between intrinsic influences (such as personal interests, values, and passion for the field) and extrinsic ones (such as external rewards, social pressure, and career prospects).

One theoretical framework increasingly used to explore motivation and well-being is the Self-Determination Theory, developed by researchers Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan (1985; 2000). This theory emerged from research in the field of motivational psychology and is based on the belief that people are naturally inclined toward growth, personal development, and social integration. [1, 2] The theory identifies three basic psychological needs: the need for competence, the need for relatedness, and the need for autonomy. When applied to the context of learning, it can be said that students who feel autonomous, competent, and socially supported are more likely to display strong intrinsic motivation, which positively influences their engagement and academic performance. Table 1 presents motivation as a continuum that ranges from a complete lack of motivation (amotivation), through various forms of extrinsic motivation (externally regulated), to intrinsic motivation, considered the most autonomous and authentic form of motivation. This approach explains the complexity of student behavior: not all students learn purely for enjoyment—they may also be motivated by rewards, social expectations, or personal values.

Table 1. The Stages of Motivation from Amotivation to Intrinsic Motivation within the Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000)

Type of Motivation	Type of Regulation	Causality	Relevant Regulatory Processes	Applicability to Learning
Amotivation	No regulation	Impersonal	Involuntary, lack of control	The student sees no meaning in learning, has no goal, or feels incapable.
Extrinsic Motivation	External regulation	External	Rewards and punishments	The student learns for grades, prizes, or to avoid punishment.
	Introjected regulation	Somewhat external	Internal pressures, guilt, shame	The student learns to avoid disappointing parents or to escape feelings of shame.
	Identified regulation	Somewhat internal	Personal acceptance of the value of learning	The student learns because they recognize its importance for their future.
Intrinsic Motivation	Integrated regulation	Internal	Congruence between learning and identity	The student integrates learning as part of their identity (e.g., “I want to become a good professional”).
	Intrinsic regulation	Internal	Interest, curiosity, enjoyment	The student learns out of passion and genuine interest in the subject.

For a student to develop authentic, deep, and lasting motivation toward the learning process, it is essential that the educational environment provides conditions that support three fundamental psychological needs. First, the need for autonomy must be respected by offering the student opportunities to make choices and have a certain degree of control over learning activities. Second, the development of competence should be encouraged so that the student gains confidence in their own abilities and perceives tasks as achievable. Third, positive relatedness is crucial, through consistent support from peers and teachers within a climate of respect and encouragement. When participation in the educational process is supported by the fulfillment of these needs, not only is academic performance improved, but the foundations are also laid for authentic, sustainable, and balanced personal and professional development.

Another relevant theory that explains students' motivation to learn is the Expectancy-Value Theory, developed by Jacquelynne S. Eccles and Allan Wigfield. This theory argues that motivation to engage in an academic task is determined by two fundamental

components: *expectancy of success*, meaning the degree to which a student believes they can succeed in a particular educational activity, and *task value*, which refers to the importance, usefulness, personal interest, or relevance of the activity in relation to the student's goals and aspirations. [3] Thus, a student will be more motivated to study at their chosen university to the extent that they believe they have a real chance of success and that their studies will bring them significant personal or professional benefits. According to the model developed by Eccles and Wigfield, these two components do not operate in isolation but are strongly influenced by personal beliefs, past experiences, self-perceptions of ability, and beliefs about the difficulty of academic tasks. Students assess their own capabilities, consider what a particular academic activity involves, and, based on this evaluation, decide whether or not it is worth engaging in. The authors propose a circular and dynamic structure in which beliefs about oneself and the task influence one's goals, and these goals, in turn, shape perceptions about academic work and motivation. [4] The values attributed to a task are defined by four dimensions:

1. Intrinsic value – the enjoyment and interest in learning;
2. Utility value – the relevance of the studies for achieving external goals (career, social status);
3. Attainment value – the connection between academic success and the ideal self-image;
4. Cost – the emotional and psychological effort involved, including negative emotions such as anxiety. [5]

In the context of choosing a university, this theory clearly explains why some students are deeply engaged in learning while others adopt a passive or unmotivated attitude. For example, a student who perceives that they have the necessary skills to meet the demands of a faculty and believes that the degree obtained will help them achieve important goals (such as a successful career) will be much more motivated to learn, participate actively, and put in consistent effort.

Another theory that explains students' learning motivation is the *self-efficacy theory*, developed by Albert Bandura. This theory is based on the idea that people are guided not only by their actual abilities but, more importantly, by what they believe about their capacity to succeed. [6] In the university context, these personal beliefs become a key factor: if a student believes they are capable of meeting the demands of their faculty, they will be more motivated to engage, learn, and persevere even when obstacles arise. When a student chooses to pursue a degree in tourism, their decision is not random but reflects a combination of internal motivational factors, some of which are well explained by self-efficacy theory.

First, the student choosing tourism consciously evaluates their level of preparation and personal competencies in relation to the field's requirements. For example, a young person who feels comfortable communicating with others, learns foreign languages easily, and is attracted to world cultures will consider that they possess the necessary skills to study and work in tourism. This positive perception of their own efficacy will en-

courage them to actively participate in learning activities, attend classes, and prepare thoroughly—even in more technical or theoretical subjects.

Second, the expectancy of success plays an important role. If the student strongly believes they will complete their studies and secure a job in an attractive area such as tour guiding, event organization, or hotel management, this belief will keep their motivation high throughout their university years. Even when facing difficulties—a tough exam, a complex project, or a demanding internship—they will continue to put in effort because they trust their chances of success.

Likewise, motivation is supported by the value attributed to their studies. The tourism student perceives university not merely as an obligatory stage but as an opportunity to build a future that brings personal and professional satisfaction. If they are passionate about traveling, interacting with people from different cultures, or promoting local and international heritage, they will consider what they learn as truly important. This personal value attached to the field will motivate them to seek additional information, participate in tourism-related volunteering, or engage in extracurricular projects. From the perspective of self-efficacy theory [7], the motivation of a tourism student is not determined solely by external factors but is based on their beliefs about themselves: what they know they can do, what they believe they will succeed in achieving, and how much what they do matters to them.

CONCLUSIONS

Students' motivation to study at their chosen faculty cannot be reduced to a simple or single explanation; rather, it must be understood as a complex process shaped by the interaction between internal factors—such as self-efficacy, personal interests, and aspirations—and external factors, such as social expectations, institutional context, and educational support. Contemporary theories, including Self-Determination Theory, Expectancy-Value Theory, and Self-Efficacy Theory, provide a solid theoretical framework to interpret how these elements influence students' active engagement in the learning process.

From this perspective, motivation is not a fixed attribute but a dynamic and contextualized process that can be supported through adapted educational policies, sensitive pedagogical interventions, and a university environment that values autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Therefore, a deep understanding of student motivation constitutes an essential premise for optimizing the university experience and for shaping future professionals who are engaged, reflective, and balanced.

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